

SENSITIVITY OF THE COIN—TAP METHOD OF NON— DESTRUCTIVE TESTING FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The physical basis of non—destructive testing for composite structures using the coin—tap method has been investigated in this paper, and the typical criterion of inspection defects is also estimated. Meantime, the minimum detectable defect for GFRP composite laminates included different defects has been analyzed in detail. A defect with 10 mm diameter under a 2 mm thick GFRP laminate is at the margin of detectability. Therefore, the method is particularly attractive for use in the field and on laminated structures that may be porous.

INTRODUCTION

The studies have shown that the accident for space vehicles in the service is mostly caused by structure failure due to various damages. Therefore, it is very important to make non—destructive evaluation (NDE) for composite structures. Because composite materials are inhomogeneous and anisotropic, it is very difficult to detect damages with normal methods and needs improving. A new consideration of NDE for composite structures based on the coin—tap test is presented in this paper. It is well known that the coin—tap test is an old method used in the inspection of laminate, honeycomb constructions and adhesively bonded structure. The test is carried out by tapping at any point in the structure with a hammer and listening to the reflected sound. Until recently, Hagemaijer and Fassbender^[1] found that it could find more types of defect in the structure such as

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honeycomb constructions than any other technique except neutron radiography. Adams and Cawley^[2] have also recommended its use of the inspection of laminate structures.

The sound produced by tapping a structure is mainly at the the frequencies of the major structure modes of vibration, and these modes are with no relation to the position of tapping. Therefore, if the sound area and the defective area are tapped with the same impulse, the sound produced must be very similar . The difference in the sound produced when the sound and defective areas are tapped must be the result of the change of the force input.

The characteristic of the impact on the structure struck by a hammer is decided by the local impedance of the structure and the hammer. Because the damages of the structure such as delamination cause the local stiffness decrease and damping increase. The nature of the impact on the defective area is changed, and the force—time curves of the sound and defective areas can be measured by incorporating a force transducer in the hammer, as shown in Figure 1. The impact on the sound area is of shorter duration and more intense than that on the defective area, and the force—time curves can be transformed into frequency domain by FFT. The curves of frequency domain of Figure 1 is shown in Figure 2. From these curves, it can be seen that the impact on the sound area has lower energy in the case of a lower frequency, and the energy has lower rate of decreasing with the increase of frequency. While the impact on the defective area has more energy at a lower frequency, furthermore, the energy decreases rapidly with the increase of frequency. This shows the impact on the defective area can not excite the higher structural modes as strongly as the impact on the sound area. Many methods can be employed to compare the time history or frequency spectrum of the two impulsives. In other words, that is to compare the peak force, duration of impact as well as decreasing rate of amplitude with increasing frequency. The impact velocity of the hammer striking on the sound and defective areas should be controlled accurately if the impact forces are compared. In short, the coin—tap test can only be used to detect the defects in the tapping region, so it is necessary to tap each part of the structure under investigation. The schematic diagram of apparatus of the coin—tap test is shown in Figure 3. In order to ensure that the every impact velocity is same, the hammer incorporating a force transducer in its head is a solenoid actuated hammer. Because the impact velocity is very small, and the mass of the striker is also small, so the kinetic energy of the striker is approximately 3mJ. This is much lower than the energy required to propagate impact defect in the composite structures.

BASIC PRINCIPLE

When a hammer taps on the defective area of a bonded composite structure, the defective area such as delamination may be modelled with a spring whose stiffness K_d is that of the layers above the defect. In practice, K_d is infinite when the structure is complete. As the

defective area becomes larger, the spring stiffness K_d is also reduced. It's suggested that the contact stiffness of the sound area is K_c . Thus, the effective contact stiffness of defective area is the contact stiffness of the sound area in series with the defect stiffness, K_{eff} is given by :

$$K_{eff} = \frac{K_c K_d}{K_c + K_d} \quad (1)$$

It is shown that the effective contact stiffness K_{eff} increases with increasing spring stiffness K_d , and gets more close to the stiffness of the sound area. Thus, the defect detection becomes more difficult. It's suggested that the edges of defective area are a clamped, the contact stiffness of the layers above the defective area, K_d is given by :

$$K_d = \frac{PEh^3}{d^2} \quad (2)$$

Where E is Young's modulus of the layers above the defect, h is depth of defect in the structure, P is a constant decided by the effective boundary condition around the defect and the poisson ratio of layers above the defect, d is the effective defect diameter. As K_d achieves K'_d , K_{eff} is closest to the contact stiffness K_c . Therefore, K'_d is the maximum contact stiffness of detectable defective area. The minimum effective defect diameter is given by

$$d_{min} = \sqrt{\frac{PE}{K'_d}} \cdot h^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad (3)$$

From equation (2) ,it has been found that when the effective defect depth, both the stiffness of the layers above the defect K_d and the effective contact stiffness of the defect K_{eff} are reduced. Thus, the different defects can be inspected through testing the contact stiffness of the structure. Because the different contact characteristics, therefore, the defective area can be determined by comparing the impact characteristics of the sound area with that of the defective area.

ESTIMATION OF CRITERION OF INSPECTION DEFECTS

As far as we know, when a hammer taps the defective area of the composite structure, the presence of delamination or disbond results in the decrease of the stiffness of defective area. Therefore, the time history of defective area differs the time history of the sound area. By comparing the time history of defective area of impact force or the corresponding spectrum with signals of the sound area ,the defective area can be determined. For the sound structure, if the structure is rigid , the impact characteristics in a sound structure is not variable with position . However, when the structure becomes more flexible, the impact characteristics in a sound structure is some change with position.

Thus, the defective area can not be accurately determined. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a criterion which will minimize this variation.

The time history or its spectrum of two impact forces can be compared. The typical methods are comparisons of the peak force, impact duration and the decreasing rate of force with increasing frequency in the middle of the frequency range. However, all these methods have serious disadvantages. When the peak force is to be employed to detect the defect, very accurate control of the velocity of the tapping hammer prior to impact must be ensured, otherwise a higher velocity impact on the defective area could be confused with a lower velocity impact on the sound area. However, in practice, the hammer is likely to be difficult to control accurately. Similarly, the impact duration or decreasing rate of force amplitude with increasing frequency would also have difficulty to be used to accurately determine the defective area.

All the possibilities discussed above seek to inspect the defective area by using only a very small proportion of the data which is available if the time history of the impact force is measured. The methods not only discern potentially valuable information, but also makes the result very sensitive to random noise of critical data points. Several possible methods for overcoming these difficulties have been investigated, the most satisfactory one to be devised is shown in Figure 2. The areas A and B under the logarithmic graph of the spectrum shown in Figure 2 are then calculated. The defective ratio R, defined by^[2]:

$$R = \frac{B}{A+B} \quad (4)$$

Because the impact on the defective area causes the lower high frequency force component than impact on the sound area, so the R is reduced. The frequency f_b which is the boundary between regions A and B is arbitrary, but 20% to 50% of full scale frequency f_{max} , when the first minimum in the spectrum of an impact on the sound area occurs close to the full scale frequency has been shown to be a satisfactory choice. The effect on the calculation of changes in the impact force is accounted for by normalizing the results so that the zero frequency level on the two spectra to be compared is the same. Thus, the curve of defective area is shifted to curve of the sound area before the calculation is performed.

THE SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF THE COIN-TAP METHOD

Before using the coin-tap test to NDT for the structure in situ, we must analyse the sensitivity of the method and determine the minimum detectable defect. In order to determine the sensitivity of the coin-tap method, not only the difference in criterion of inspection defect is investigated when the defective area is presented in the composite structure, but also changed range of defective criterion with position in the sound struc-

ture must be determined. For a good composite structure, if the impact characteristics with position is small changed, by comparing the difference of criterion of the sound area with that of defective area, the region of defective area can be accurate determined. Thus, this method has higher sensitivity, otherwise the sensitivity of the method is smaller.

In order to determine the sensitivity of the coin—tap method used to inspection composite structure, the $[0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]_s$ GFRP composite specimens including ten circular disbonds of different sizes are used in this study, the dimensions of the GFRP specimen that was modeled are $250 \times 250 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$.

where diameter	of	1"	defective area = 30mm
diameter	of	2"	defective area = 25mm
diameter	of	3"	defective area = 22mm
diameter	of	4"	defective area = 20mm
diameter	of	5"	defective area = 18mm
diameter	of	6"	defective area = 16mm
diameter	of	7"	defective area = 14mm
diameter	of	8"	defective area = 12mm
diameter	of	9"	defective area = 10mm
diameter	of	10"	defective area = 20mm

In order to research edge effects of defect, the defect 9" and 10" are introduced within about 20 mm from the edge. Figure 4 shows the map of defect locations in GFRP laminate. The map of ultrasonic C—scans is shown in Figure 5. The results of all the tests on this composite laminate are summarised in Table 1. From table 1, it has been found that the impact duration increases and the peak force decreases when defective area increases. However, the peak force of some larger defect is higher than that above smaller defect. It has been seen that the tests of using peak force measurements as an criterion of defect have serious drawbacks. Except the 9" and 10" defects, the impact durations of all defective areas are higher than that of sound areas away from the edges of the specimen, so the defects may be detected. However, for the 9" and 10" defects close to the edges of the laminate, if the impact characteristics of the sound area away from the edges may be used as the deflection criterion, the defect detection becomes more difficult. It has been seen that the impact duration of the sound area away from edges is higher than that of the 9" and 10" defective areas. Therefore, only by comparing the impact characteristics of the defective area with the impact characteristics of the sound area close to the edge, the defects near the edge of laminate can be detected. Similarly, by comparing defective ratio R in the table 1, the results will clarify the extent of the edge effects. From the discussion above, it has been found that the defect criterion R of the sound area is nearly the same with the R of the defective area when the diameter of defect is reduced to 10 mm, and R is 0.57 and 0.58 respectively. Therefore, a defect of 10mm diameter under 2 mm thick GFRP laminate is at the margin of detectability.

SUMMARY

From the discussion and test above, it can be seen that the advantage of the coin—tap method over ultrasonic method is

- (1) no couplant is needed between the testing structure and tapping hammer;
- (2) no transducer need be attached to the structure;
- (3) not sensitive to background noise;

Therefore, the coin—tap method is particularly attractive for use in the field, and on laminated structures that may be porous.

REFERENCES

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Figure 1 Force-time histories of the sound and defective areas of GFRP laminate

Figure 2 Spectra of time histories shown in Figure 1

Figure 3 Schematic diagram of apparatus of the coin-tap test

Figure 4 The map of defecte locations in GFRP laminate

Figure 5 Map of ultrasonic C-Scans of GFRP laminate

TABLE 1 $F_{max} = 4.0\text{KHz}$ $F_b = 0.25F_{max}$

defect criterion (R)	Sound areas		Defective areas									
	away from the edge	20mm from the edge	1"	2"	3"	4"	5"	6"	7"	8"	9"	10"
	0.53	0.58	0.4	0.46	0.50	0.48	0.49	0.51	0.52	0.51	0.57	0.54
Impact peak force	28.4	30.0	13.6	21.2	21.6	20.0	22.0	26.0	22.0	28.6	28.6	24.2
Impact duration (ns)	693	594	1188	825	792	792	759	726	726	726	627	660